

Supply Chain Flexibility and Collaboration Strategies on Performance of Fast Food Chains in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the supply chain flexibilities and collaboration strategies vis-a-vis the performance of fast food firms in South-South region of Nigeria. The study adopted an explanatory survey research design. The target population was all fast food firms in the South-South region of Nigeria (Kawai, 2022). The research population was 499 fast food firms in the South-South, Nigeria and 10,064 employees. Taro Yamane was used to determine a sample size of 385 staff in five departments in each of the firms sampled. A four-point Likert scale questionnaire was administered to senior level managers with the knowledge of supply-chain and logistics functions. Both descriptive and inferential analysis was done using SPSS to find out the influence of supply chain risk management strategies on performance of fast food firms in South-South, Nigeria (Nyang'au, 2017). The study established that both the supply chain flexibilities strategies and collaboration strategies have significant effect on performance of fast food firms (Nyang'au, 2017). It calls for the adoption of proactive strategies to deal with supply chain risks and vulnerabilities in a bid to secure and institute a responsive and effective supply chain systems. This study concludes that the most important Supply Chain Risk Management strategies on the performance of a fast food firm are flexibility strategies. The study recommends, among others, that fast food firms should adopt risk control strategies that allow collaboration with their supply chain members for their business as a matter of necessity, as this will help to protect them against risk.

Keywords: *Supply Chain, Risk Management, Collaboration, Flexibility Strategies, Performance.*

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Introduction

The susceptibility of supply networks to disruptions has seen a rise in recent times and has garnered significant interest from both industry professionals and scholars (Skipper & Hanna, 2009). The field of supply chain management is associated with a multitude of dangers, as highlighted by Munyuko (2015). The potential hazards associated with this context are supplier risk, production risk, environmental risk, technology risk, transportation risk, warehousing risk, and financial risk (Ahmad, et al., 2019). The

process of mitigating these risks is often known as supply chain risk management. Effective risk mitigation is crucial for the survival and growth of any business, especially in dynamic and volatile industries like the fast food sector. Risk mitigation strategies can be broadly categorized into four main approaches: risk avoidance, risk reduction, risk sharing, and risk acceptance. Risk avoidance involves eliminating or avoiding the risk entirely, such as by not engaging in certain high-risk activities or markets (Diverse Daily, n.d.). Risk reduction aims to minimize the likelihood or impact of a risk through measures like implementing robust operational controls, diversifying suppliers, or investing in backup systems. Risk sharing distributes the risk among multiple stakeholders, such as through insurance policies or collaborative supply chain partnerships. Risk acceptance acknowledges that some risks are unavoidable and instead focuses on developing contingency plans to manage their consequences.

According to Sundquist, Gadde, and Hulthén (2018), the proficient handling of supply chain disruptions has the potential to mitigate avoidable expenses, minimise delays, and reduce the need for additional work caused by quality problems in projects. Organisations that possess supply chains characterised by advanced risk management capabilities are able to swiftly rebound from the negative consequences of disruptions, hence gaining a competitive edge (Gurtu & Johny, 2021). The complexity of business transactions, technological advances, globalization, speed of product cycles, and the overall pace of change have increased uncertainty, fragility, vulnerability and disruptions facing organizations (Wagner & Bode 2006; Coleman 2006; Nyang'au, 2017). For these reasons, supply chain risk management (SCRM) is becoming an integral part of risk management in most organisations (Tomlin, 2006; Ghagde, Dani & Kalawsky, 2013; Nyang'au, 2017).

According to Killackey (2009), it is important for firms to ensure that their risk management programmes are effectively linked with their strategies at several levels, such as the business strategy level. According to Acharyya and Johnson (2007), the results of these initiatives should provide data that may be used to ascertain company goals and develop suitable corporate strategies. The alignment of risk management programmes with business strategy is essential in order to comprehensively address the whole spectrum of risks within an organization's hierarchy. Organisations are increasingly recognising the need of implementing risk management methods in order to effectively navigate the market disruptions resulting from fluctuations in supply chains (Ochieng, 2019). According to Burer, Jones, and Lowe (2008), this particular method has the ability to facilitate the concentration of managers, risk analysts, and stakeholders on the mitigation of possible dangers.

Upon observing risk management as a managerial framework, it is essential that the effectiveness of risk management not only yields concrete benefits for the organisation but also served as a means to facilitate cognitive and behavioural learning processes inside the organisation. According to Huber and Herman (2011), risk management is considered an essential component of effective corporate management. The establishment of a robust risk management culture would facilitate the development of a management system that prioritises the risk appetite as a crucial factor influencing performance outcomes. However, it is worth noting that the focus on supply chain performance and the associated risks of disruptions within the fast food and agricultural sector has been relatively limited in both academic research and practical applications (Wegner & Bode, 2006). The present research is driven by the objective of assessing the effect of supply chain risk management strategies on performance among fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria (Nyang'au, 2017).

Theoretical and Conceptual Clarifications

Supply Chain Risk Management

Supply chain risk (SCR) is defined as uncertain and unreliable events in the supply chain system causing disruption and increasing the opportunity of negative consequences in the supply chain (Tang & Musa, 2011; Faizal & Palaniappan, 2014; Aqlan, & Lam, 2016). The SCR includes every event that may occur,

even a small event, and every event which results in any negative influence on the supply chain system (Tang, & Musa, 2011; Aqlan, & Lam, 2016). Faizal and Palaniappan (2014) reported that risk's sources could be from the upstream side (supply risk), downstream side (demand risk), and from manufacturing process, i.e. process risk. Risk always exists in the supply chain since uncertain circumstance affects the supply chain performance (Aqlan, & Lam, 2016). The supply chain can be vulnerable to risk when it faces uncertain events, and they will be in a rough position (Ganguly, & Chatterjee, 2016). According to Porterfield, MacDonald and Griffis (2012), supply chain risks have negative effects on the stock market and operational performance. On a similar note, supply chain risks can directly affect corporate stock prices by nearly 9 per cent and revenue losses by 20 per cent (Benyoucef & Forzley, 2007; Al Aziz, et al., 2018). In addition, supply chain risks can have long-term negative effects on a firm's financial performance (Tang, 2006; Al Aziz, et al., 2018)). The significant negative impact of supply chain risk on customers is that the disruption hinders the ability of producing firms from meeting customers' demands as at when due (Al Aziz, et al., 2018).

Supply Chain Flexibility Strategies

Supply chain flexibility is a reflection of an organization's ability to respond to an operational process that is effective and efficient against changes or constraints (Sezen, 2008; Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). Proactive supply chains must be flexible and easily adapt to the needs of their partners and environmental conditions in the limit/minimum time (Stevenson & Spring, 2007; Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). Flexibility is aimed at the organization and inventory in the overall supply chain. Flexibility creates supply chain resilience by increasing flexibility in urgent situations (Christopher & Holweg, 2011; Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). Supply chain flexibility strategy allows food and beverage manufacturers to react to unforeseen events such as short delivery delays, uncertain demands as well as natural disasters (Nyang'au, 2017). According to Liu *et al.* (2010) firms that achieve higher levels of flexibility and agility significantly outperform their less flexible counterparts. Flexible firms are more innovative, dynamic and responsive to changes and challenges (Gligor & Holcomb, 2012; Tang & Tomlin, 2009; Nyang'au, 2017). Flexibility positively impacts its ability to enhance comparative performance relative to leading industry competitors. Nembhard *et al.* (2005) noted that a manufacturing firm can have the flexibility to select different suppliers, plant locations, and market regions (Nyang'au, 2017). Flexibility is significant for supply chains that face demand and supply risks since flexibility helps a firm reallocate resources quickly and smoothly in response to change (Nyang'au, 2017). In volatile and uncertain environments, dynamic capabilities such as flexibility can be harnessed to achieve growth (Nyang'au, 2017).

Supply Chain Collaboration Strategies

Collaboration between supply chain members emphasizes how cooperation can support supply chain efficiency and provide strategic knowledge to improve food supply chain performance (Jüttner & Maklan, 2011; Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). Collaboration across the entire supply chain can significantly help reduce risk. The basic principle of collaborative work in the supply chain is the exchange of information to reduce uncertainty (Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). The main priority for risk reduction must be the creation of supply chain communication for information exchange between supply chain members (Ireland, 2002; Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). Horizontal collaboration occurs between organizations that work at the same level, usually in partnership, or different functional departments (Afifa, & Santoso, 2022). Collaboration is important both before and during the problem but also after the problem it would also be good to continue, with the aim of increasing the ability of the system to achieve the future (Sheffi, 2005; Afifa, & Santoso, 2022).

Organizational Performance

Organisational performance is widely recognised as a fundamental concept in the field of management, and many managerial responsibilities are designed with this notion in mind. Indeed, the performance of organisations can serve as a reflection of their success (Amin, 2017). According to Amin (2017), organisational performance is defined as the collective achievements attained by many businesses or

departments inside an organisation. These achievements are associated with an organisational objective within a specified timeframe. The objective can be intended for a particular phase or for the full scope (Lee & Huang, 2012). The concept of organisational performance is closely linked to the long-term viability and achievement of an organisation (Ahmed & Shafiq, 2014). Performance in an organisational context refers to the extent to which an employee successfully carries out the objectives and goals of the organisation inside the workplace (Cascio, 2006). The role of an individual is determined by the extent to which they fulfill specific targets or objectives that establish performance boundaries (Cascio, 2006). Organisational performance refers to the evaluation of an organization's efficacy and efficiency in relation to the metrics outlined in its mandate (Rogers, 2016). The implementation of a performance assessment system facilitates the enhancement of an organization's ability to effectively pursue and attain its goals and objectives.

Empirical Review

Hadyait, Ahmad, and Rashid (2019) examined the impact of supply chain risk management variables on organisational performance. Three primary variables for managing supply chain risks were identified: supply chain risk identification, supply chain risk sources, and supply chain risk mitigation (Al Aziz, et al., 2018). The research discovered that the risk register approach is mostly employed for the purpose of identifying hazards inside the supply chain at various levels (Al Aziz, et al., 2018). The report identifies several significant hazards, namely supplier risks, environmental risks, political risks, market risks, warehousing risks, and financial risks (Al Aziz, et al., 2018). In the realm of supply chain risk management, there exist several effective mitigation strategies aimed at minimising potential risks ((Al Aziz, et al., 2018)). These strategies encompass risk avoidance measures, risk control measures, and risk cooperation measures. The research findings indicate that proactive identification of risks by an organisation is of utmost significance, particularly during the initial stages of the decision-making process. The identification of various risk categories is crucial across all stages of supply chain processes. Once all hazards have been identified, the organisation must proceed to reduce these risks by implementing various solutions outlined in a mitigation strategy.

Solomon, et al., (2018) conducted a study on analysis of business risks of fast food firms in Calabar metropolis, Cross-River State (Solomon, et al., 2018). The study analyzed business risk of fast food firms in Calabar metropolis, Cross-River State, Nigeria. Specifically, it assessed the operations of fast food businesses, analyzed rate of growth of the firms, evaluated the different risks involved and determine the effect of risk variables on their performance (profit) (Solomon, et al., 2018). Both primary and secondary data were used while data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics, business risk model and multiple regression analytical technique (Solomon, et al., 2018). The results revealed that 75.6% of the firms source their raw materials from the markets; their mean growth rate was 5.78 with a mean coefficient of variation of 67.16%, showing that most firms were exposed to high level of risk (Solomon, et al., 2018). The regression results revealed that business risk, volume of sales, age of the firms, variable costs, business equity growth rate and total revenue were significant on profit (Solomon, et al., 2018). Consequently, the study recommended that, in setting up a fast food business, the social setting of the people particularly their food preferences should be considered, managing variable costs through bulk purchases could improve the profit of these firms and that the significant variables should be considered for optimum performance and sustainability (Solomon, et al., 2018).

Cui and Basnet (2015) examined an exploratory study of supply chain risk management in the New Zealand fast food industry. The study reports on exploratory qualitative research into the current practice of supply chain risk management in the New Zealand fast food industry (Cui, & Basnet, 2015). The study found that the New Zealand fast food industry depends heavily on import from other countries and overseas suppliers for the large amount of raw materials required by the industry (Cui, & Basnet, 2015). These suppliers hold dominant power in New Zealand fast food industry. As a result, fast-food restaurants have limited room for switching to contingency suppliers in disruptive situations, such as natural disasters or earthquakes (Cui, & Basnet, 2015). Furthermore, the study also shows that the fast

food industry has increased vulnerability due to the stringent food safety and health standards and customer’s increasing awareness of food safety issues (Cui, & Basnet, 2015).

Materials and Methods

This study adopts the explanatory survey design (Nyang’au, 2017). Explanatory research implies that the research in question is intended to explain, rather than simply to describe, the phenomena studied (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009; Nyang’au, 2017). The South-south region as the study area comprises of six States, which are: Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo and Rivers. It is located between latitudes 5° 00'N and 6° 30'N and longitudes 5° 20'E and 9° 00'E as seen in Figure 1 (Ita-Nya, 2020). The South-south region with the Niger River is sitting directly on the Gulf of Guinea on the Atlantic Ocean in Nigeria (Ita-Nya, 2020).

Figure 1. South-South States and their Capital Cities

Source: Open Street Mapping, 2022

The target populations for this study are managers, procurement or purchasing officers, logistics officers, warehousing or store officers and supervisors of fast food chains in South-South Nigeria with annual sales between 5,000,000 and 20,000,000 million Naira with as well as a minimum number of 10 employees that have been in business longer than 5 years (Ukorebi, 2018). The actual population of fast food firms in the South-South region of Nigeria was four hundred and ninety-nine (499) firms with ten thousand and sixty-four (10,064) employees. Taro Yamane was used to determine the sample size of 385. Purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants for this study because it allowed the researcher to engage participants with relevant experience and knowledge about the fast food business (Ukorebi, 2018). Questionnaire instrument was used to collect data from the participants, while descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used for the analysis (Olugbenga, et al., 2025). The data were presented using frequency and percentage tables, while the hypotheses were tested using the Spearman Rank Order Correlation analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 361)

S/N	Variables	Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Male	163	45.2%

		Female	198	54.8%
2	Age Range	18 – 27 Years	92	25.48%
		28 – 37 Years	115	31.86%
		38 – 47 Years	115	31.86%
		48 Years & Above	39	10.80%
3	Marital Status	Single	116	32.1%
		Married	202	55.96%
		Separated	17	4.7%
		Divorced	26	7.2%
4	Educational Qualification	Secondary	81	22.4%
		Tertiary	280	77.6%
5	Average Monthly Income	Less than N30,000	38	10.5%
		N30,000 – N70,000	165	45.7%
		N71,000 – N100,000	106	29.4%
		N101,000 & Above	52	14.4%
6	Position/Department in the Organization	Manager	71	19.7%
		Procurement/Purchasing	71	19.7%
		Logistics Officer	70	19.4%
		Warehousing/Store	66	18.3%
		Supervisor	83	23.0%
7	Years of Experience in the Current Firm	1 – 5 Years	150	41.6%
		6 – 10 Years	173	47.9%
		11 – 15 Years	38	10.5%
8	Number of Employees	10 – 49	361	100%
9	Age/Length of Time in Existence	6 – 10 Years	209	57.9%
		11 – 15 Years	139	38.5%
		16 – 20 Years	13	3.6%

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

The result was carried out in line with the objectives which the study was set to achieve. The result is presented as follows (Egba, Obafemi, & Eludoyin, 2023):

Socio-Economics Characteristics of Respondents

Table 1 presents the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. Item #1 indicates the gender distribution of the respondents and shows that 54.8% were female, while 45.2% were male. Item #2 shows the age distribution of the respondents and reveals that 31.86% of respondents were jointly within the 28 - 37 years and 38 - 47 years, while 25.48%, and 10.8% of respondents were within 18 – 27 years and 48 years and above respectively. In addition, item #3 revealed that 55.96% of the respondents were married, while 32.1% were single. Item #4 revealed the educational attainment of the respondents that further revealed that 77.6% and 22.4% of respondents had tertiary education and secondary education respectively. The sixth item (i.e., item #6) on the tables indicates the position and department of the respondents from which 19.7% of respondents were jointly managers, as well as procurement officers, 19.4% were logistics officers, 18.3% were in warehousing and store department, and 23% were supervisors.

The employee size of the firms in the study area is presented in Table 1 as item #8 showing that all the firms 100% of total respondents had 10 - 49 employees. Finally, the age and length of time the fast food firms have been in existence (item #9) reveals that majority (57.9%) of the fast food outlets had been in existence between 6 – 10 years, 38.5% of the total respondents said their fast food outlets had been in existence between 11 – 15 years, while 3.6% said their fast food outlets had been in existence between 16 – 20 years. The implication is that all the fast food firms 100% that participated in the study have been in business longer than 5 years, which is one of the criteria for participation.

Influence of Supply Chain Risk Flexibility Strategies on Performance

From tables 2, item Q#F1, it can be inferred that respondents who agreed that their fast food outlets store items at appropriate distribution points close to the customers in the supply (Nyang'au, 2017) had the highest response of 71.5% while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 8.9%. Also, in item Q#F1, the high mean score of 3.10 indicates that majority of the respondents agreed (Etim, Emenike, & Wizer, 2022) that their fast food outlets store items at appropriate distribution points close to the customers in the supply (Nyang'au, 2017). Since the mean score of 3.10 is ≥ 2.5 (Etim, Emenike, & Wizer, 2022), we thereby accept the statement that the fast food outlets in South-South, Nigeria do store items at appropriate distribution points close to the customers in the supply (Nyang'au, 2017). In item Q#F2, respondents that strongly agreed that their fast food outlets do accommodate several customer service requirements had the highest response of 64.8% while those who strongly disagreed had the lowest response of 3.6%. Also, the high mean score of 3.53 indicates that majority of the respondents agreed that their fast food outlets do accommodate several customer service requirements (Etim, Emenike, & Wizer, 2022).

Also in item Q#F3, respondents who strongly disagreed that their fast food outlets quickly reorganize supply chain resources immediately to respond to supply chain risks (Nyang'au, 2017) had the highest response of 53.2% while those who agreed had the lowest response of 9.7%. The low mean score of 1.83 also indicates that majority of the respondents disagreed (Etim, Emenike, & Wizer, 2022) that their fast food outlets quickly reorganize supply chain resources immediately to respond to supply chain risks (Nyang'au, 2017). Item Q#F7 revealed that respondents who disagreed that in their fast food firms, there is increased efficiency in the process of delivering goods had the highest response of 69.3% while those who strongly agreed had the lowest response of 8.9%. The low mean score of 2.15 also indicates that majority of the respondents disagreed (Etim, Emenike, & Wizer, 2022).

Table 2. Influence of Supply Chain Risk Flexibility Strategies on Performance

Items	Strongly Disagree Freq (%)	Disagree Freq (%)	Agree Freq (%)	Strongly Agree Freq (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
Stores items at appropriate distribution points close to the customers in the supply		32 (8.9%)	258 (71.5%)	58 (19.7%)	3.1037	.52388
Accommodate several customer service Requirements	13 (3.6%)	14 (3.9%)	100 (27.7%)	234 (64.8%)	3.5318	.74286
Quickly reorganize supply chain resources immediately to respond to supply chain risks	192 (53.2%)	87 (24.1%)	35 (9.7%)	47 (13.0%)	1.8261	1.06020
Preparation of a set of action plans for unexpected disruptions			186 (51.5%)	175 (48.5%)	3.4849	.50061
We have introduced new products and services		16 (4.4%)	43 (11.9%)	302 (83.7%)	3.7926	.50216
The total cost of acquisition of raw materials is reduced		16 (4.4%)	306 (84.8%)	39 (10.8%)	3.0635	.38335
There is increased efficiency in the process of delivering goods	43 (11.9%)	250 (69.3%)	36 (10.0%)	32 (8.9%)	2.1538	.73941

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

Effect of Supply Chain Risk Collaboration Strategies on Performance

From tables 3, item Q#CO1 shows that respondents who agreed that their fast food outlets do exchange information that helps in reducing the supply chain risks had the highest response of 72.9% while those who strongly disagreed had the lowest response of 4.7% (Etim, Emenike, & Wizer, 2022). The high mean

score of 3.13 indicates that majority of the respondents agreed. Since the mean score of 3.13 is ≥ 2.5 , we thereby accept the statement that the fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria do exchange information that helps in reducing the supply chain risks (Etim, Emenike, & Wizor, 2022). In addition, item Q#CO2 shows that respondents who agreed that their fast food firms do have collaboration with supply chain partners had the highest response of 71.5% while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 4.4%. Also, the high mean score of 3.06 further indicates that majority of the respondents agreed (Etim, Emenike, & Wizor, 2022).

Also in item Q#CO4, respondents who agreed that in their fast food chains there is early supplier involvement in the development of specifications had the highest response of 70.1% while the remaining respondents with response of 29.9% strongly agreed. The high mean score of 3.30 further indicates that majority of the respondents agreed that in their fast food outlets there is early supplier involvement in the development of specifications (Etim, Emenike, & Wizor, 2022). Item Q#CO6 shows that respondents who agreed that in their fast food chains, there exist a transparent logistical system on transportation and delivery of goods had the highest response of 46.2% while those who disagreed had the lowest response of 17.4%. Also the high mean score of 3.19 indicates that majority of the respondents agreed. Since the mean score of 3.19 is ≥ 2.5 , we thereby accept the statement that the fast food chains in South-South, Nigeria have a transparent logistical system on transportation and delivery of goods (Etim, Emenike, & Wizor, 2022).

Table 3. Effect of Supply Chain Risk Collaboration Strategies on Performance

S/N	Items	Strongly Disagree Freq (%)	Disagree Freq (%)	Agree Freq (%)	Strongly Agree Freq (%)	Mean	Std. Deviation
CO1	Exchange of information that helps in reducing the supply chain risks	17 (4.7%)		263 (72.9%)	81 (22.4%)	3.1304	.62903
CO2	Collaboration with supply chain partners.	17 (4.7%)	16 (4.4%)	258 (71.5%)	70 (19.4%)	3.0569	.65033
CO3	Involvement of supply chain partners in the new product design, development effort and marketing			283 (78.4%)	78 (21.6%)	3.2174	.41316
CO4	There is early supplier involvement in the development of specifications			253 (70.1%)	108 (29.9%)	3.2977	.45800
CO5	Goods and services are made available to the consumers at cheaper rates	242 (67.0%)	38 (10.5%)	81 (22.4%)	73 (20.2%)	1.5585	.83891
CO6	There exist a transparent logistical system on transportation and delivery of goods		63 (17.5%)	167 (46.3%)	131 (36.3%)	3.1906	.70979

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Supply chain risk flexibility strategies have no significant influence on performance of fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria.

Table 4. Correlations Result for Hypothesis One

			Flexibility Strategies	Performance
Spearman's rho	Flexibility Strategies	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.715**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	361	361
	Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.715**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	361	361
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Source: Research Data, 2025

From the result obtained in table 4, the correlation coefficient (rho) showed that supply chain risk flexibility strategies have a significant influence on performance of fast food outlets in South-South, Nigeria (Nyang'au, 2017). The correlation coefficient of 0.715 confirms the extent and strength of this influence and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. The coefficient represents a strong correlation between the variables (Nyang'au, 2017). Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld (Nyang'au, 2017). Thus, the supply chain risk flexibility strategies have positive and significant influence on performance of fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria (Nyang'au, 2017). These findings are in consonance with those of Gligor and Holcomb (2012) that found out that firms that achieve higher levels of flexibility and agility significantly outperform their less flexible counterparts (Nyang'au, 2017). Flexible firms are more innovative, dynamic and responsive to changes and challenges. Hence, flexibility positively impacts its ability to enhance comparative performance relative to leading industry competitors. The outcome of this study is also consistent with Mensah, Diyuoh, and Oppong (2014); Karimi and Rafiee (2014) (Nyang'au, 2017).

H₀₂: Supply chain risk collaboration strategies have no significant influence on performance of fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria.

Table 5. Correlations Result for Hypothesis Two

			Collaboration Strategies	Performance
Spearman's rho	Collaboration Strategies	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.441**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	361	361
	Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.441**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	361	361
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				

Source: Research Data, 2025

From the result obtained in table 5, the correlation coefficient (rho) showed that supply chain risk collaboration strategies have a significant effect on performance of fast food chains in South-South, Nigeria. The correlation coefficient of 0.441 confirms the extent and strength of this influence and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$ (Nwinyokpugi, & Ejiowhor, 2019). Therefore, based on empirical findings the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected and the alternate upheld. Thus, the supply chain risk collaboration strategies have positive and significant effect on performance of fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria (Nyang'au, 2017). These findings are in tandem with Wieland and Wallenburg (2012) who revealed that communicative and collaborative relationships have a positive effect on supply chain resilience (Nyang'au, 2017). It is also found that improved resilience, obtained by investing in agility and robustness, enhances a supply chain's customer value (Nyang'au, 2017). Similarly, Srinivasan *et al.*

(2011) stated that building trust in relationships contribute to reduction of supply chain related risks. Therefore, Supply chain risk collaboration strategies have positive effect on performance of fast food firms in South-South, Nigeria (Nyang'au, 2017).

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, in a changing and challenging environment, fast food businesses must advance their supply chains beyond the traditional (Nyang'au, 2017). Without a strategic focus on supply-chain risk management, supply chain operations can rapidly deteriorate, putting quality, profitability, and lives in danger (Nyang'au, 2017). From a managerial standpoint, it becomes important to understand and actively manage all the supply chain disruptions that influence business performance and continuity of organizations. Firms need to realize the importance of their supply chain resilience capabilities that are crucial during the supply chain disruptions (Nyang'au, 2017). The implementation of supply chain risk management strategies such as flexibility and collaboration is necessary to ensure the continuity of businesses (Nyang'au, 2017). Based on the above empirical findings, it can be concluded that, Supply chain risk management strategies have significant influence on the performance of fast food chains in South-South region of Nigeria (Tilaye, 2024).

Based on the fact that collaboration often leads to better supply chain coordination, the study thereby recommends the need for fast food to implement collaborative strategies with the suppliers to reduce and prevent the occurrence of supply chain risks (Nyang'au, 2017). For this, mutual and corporate trust and information sharing among supply chain firms and the off-taker fast food should be strengthened with the commitment to share risk and joint investment. This strategy does not only have the potentials of achieving improvement of flexibility and supply chain performance, it could also provide the ground for achieving a resilient supply chain operations through collaborative planning, visibility, and supply chain resilient culture (Nyang'au, 2017).

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